

Research of Aviation PM Technologies, mOdeling and Regulation - RAPTOR

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Report with Regulatory Framework

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

*This report describes the current regulatory framework and technical evidence on proposed work items. The purpose of this document is to identify knowledge gaps in the subject area of **RAPTOR** - Research of Aviation PM Technologies, mOdelling and Regulation – and where outcomes from RAPTOR may help fill some of these knowledge gaps. Finally, the report aims to identify and articulate further future research needs in this area and will set out a road map for future work and help establish a co-ordinated action to bring together the regulatory community and associate stakeholders. (This report is a joint deliverable for D3.1, D3.2 and D3.5)*

RAPTOR contributes to the following areas related to aviation PM emissions: measurement uncertainties and regulation at engine exit plane (WP4); modelling transport, dispersion and transformation of engine emissions (WP5); and health impacts (WP6). WP3 aims to coordinate, communicate and provide a regulatory overview of these technical work packages.

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List of Abbreviations

CAEP Committee for Aviation and Environmental Protection

CPC Condensation Particle Counters

DMA Differential Mobility Analyzer

EASA European Union Aviation Safety Agency

EU European Union

ICAO International Civil Aviation Organisation

kN kilonewton

LII Laser Induced Incandescence

LOD Limit Of Detection

LTO Landing and Take Off cycle
MSS Micro Soot Sensor
nvPM non-volatile particulate matter
PM total particulate matter (vPM + nvPM)
SARPs Standards and Recommended Practices
SMPS Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer
UFP Ultra Fine Particles
vPM volatile particulate matter
VPR Volatile Particle Remover
WHO World Health Organisation

1 Introduction

WP3 provides a focus for the project and delivers against all four high level objectives set out in the work programme. The key actions are to:

- i) support EASA in the field of PM regulation;
- ii) identify knowledge gaps and set out a road map for future work and establish a co-ordinated action to bring together the regulatory community and associated stakeholders.

The WP3 tasks are outlined below and this Deliverable (3.1) touches on most of these tasks.

This report aims to provide a summary of the key findings of the other WPs (particularly WP4) in terms of the current and future regulatory framework for aircraft engine emissions, to support the work of EASA in the field of PM regulation and the input to the ICAO-CAEP international regulations. In addition, some of the WP5 and WP6 findings are used to indicate potential future regulatory directions.

Engine Emission Regulations

The results from WP4 (Particulate Matter (PM) Measurement work package) are consolidated here to aid communication of WP4 outputs to the regulatory community, helping to fill knowledge gaps for the engine certification procedures (ICAO-CAEP, E31 and EASA). WP4 provides insights into the understanding of the uncertainties associated with the current nvPM CAEP standards. WP4 also has provided some analysis work on emissions data of nvPM (mass and number) from small engines (less or equal 26.7 kN) which are currently not regulated by the CAEP/10 or CAEP/11 nvPM mass and number standards.

Ambient Concentration Regulations

WP5 is largely a review work package of ICAO-CAEP and European databases, models and research activities for the estimation of aircraft PM mass and number assessment. WP5 has leveraged new modelling research work undertaken including the H2020 AVIATOR project. WP3 has aided WP5 in providing the link directly to the ICAO-CAEP modelling and database

group (MDG) and to WG3 leading to updates to the ICAO Doc 9889 (the ICAO airport air quality manual) which is the international standard guidance for the airports community, helping practitioners to use fit for purpose methodologies for assessment of local air quality in and around airports with a consistent approach. WP6 has undertaken a literature review on the toxicity of aircraft engine PM emissions and collated the information available. WP6 also collected new experimental data from filter samples collected in WP4. Both WP5 and WP6 have identified knowledge gaps and further research is required before new regulatory directions could be determined. In particular: WP5 recommends developing better characterization of vPM emissions and the development in the plume is required to better assess the contribution to overall PM ambient concentrations; WP6 recommends the development of a standardised protocol for hazard assessment in which characterisation of the exhaust in terms of physical-chemical properties are combined with toxicity and a dose-response relationship is developed. Ultimately, in combination with composition an aggregated hazard index can be constructed incorporating the relative contribution to health effects, prioritized based on the estimated contribution to local PM concentrations.

WP3 tasks and summary of outcomes:

Task 3.1 Regulatory Framework

Working with the regulatory community, in particular EASA, WP3 has provided an assessment of current evidence to identify knowledge gaps (D3.3). As work has progressed within the other WPs (WP4, WP5 and WP6) a final issue of the regulatory outcomes is provided here (D3.1).

Task 3.2 Maintenance of ICAO-CAEP Annex 16 Volume II and ETM Volume II guidance

As work in WP4 has progressed, the outputs aim to reduce uncertainties associated with measurements undertaken for engine certification measurements, including calibration uncertainties. WP4 has also worked to provide information on uncertainties associated with ambient conditions during measurement, certification test fuel composition and system loss correction. These project outputs will aid the regulators in the maintenance, and updating where relevant, of the ICAO-CAEP Annex 16 Volume II and ETM Volume II guidance:

Standards and Recommended Practices (Annex 16 Vol II, Part III, Chapter 4 and associated Appendices).

Task 3.3 Synergizing RAPTOR outcomes to support EASA and the EU

WP3 has supported and worked alongside the technical WPs to ensure high level engagement of the regulatory and policy making community and develop a roadmap to help narrow knowledge gaps. As RAPTOR outcomes are delivered appropriate communication and dissemination routes have been utilised to ensure the efficient and effective engagement with the end user community. The pace of WP3 has effectively been dictated by the rhythms of the technical work packages – as these have been, to some extent, slowed by the impact of COVID-19. The outcomes of RAPTOR will continue to be disseminated to ICAO-CAEP_WG3 and SAE E31 in the early months of the CAEP/13 cycle starting in March 2022.

Task 3.4 Establish and embed plan for exploitation and dissemination of results (PEDR)

WP3 issued an agreed Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Research (PEDR) for the RAPTOR project which guides the successful communication, dissemination and exploitation of outcomes. RAPTOR was a coordinating partner of an international health focused workshop which brought together various projects in Europe and North America to share knowledge, discuss and debate the impact of aviation PM on health. Through WP3 the RAPTOR community is helping to create new links between the research communities from the aviation certification measurements and regulations, the local air quality and the health fields.

Task 3.5 Communication of RAPTOR and promotion of its results

Internal Communication - Project Meetings

Formal meetings of RAPTOR have taken place according to the agreed schedule:

- Advisory Board meetings: once a year (November 2019).
- General Assembly meetings: once a year (November 2019).
- Executive Board meetings: every 6 months (since March 2019 these have taken place on a more frequent schedule to facilitate planning for our response to COVID-19).

- Work packages Coordination meeting: Most WP meet (remotely) informally on a monthly basis.

Agendas and minutes of formal meetings are located on the RAPTOR Sharepoint platform.

External Communication with stakeholders

As RAPTOR has developed during the period of the global pandemic, the importance of making outcomes has been reinforced with respect to the following: i) as widely available as possible; ii) communicating in a tone and level which is readily understood; and iii) contribute to the body of knowledge and understanding of aircraft emissions in and around airports. Project partners have had to adapt to the impact that the Covid pandemic has had on usual communication and dissemination routes. But in general RAPTOR has been able to build its profile within the stakeholder community.

2 Background: Current Regulations

2.1 Emission Regulations: ICAO Standards

Standards limiting the emissions of smoke, nvPM (as maximum mass concentration), nvPM mass and number LTO emissions, unburnt hydrocarbons (HC), carbon monoxide (CO) and oxides of nitrogen (NOx) from turbojet and turbofan aircraft engines are contained in Annex 16 Volume II¹ to the Convention on International Civil Aviation (the Chicago Convention). The nvPM emissions SARPs can be found in ICAO-CAEP Annex 16 Volume II and ETM Volume II guidance: Standards and Recommended Practices, Part III, Chapter 4.

2.1.1 nvPM mass concentration standard (CAEP/10 Standard)

Before 2016, the only emission standard related to PM emissions was the Smoke Number regulation which effectively requires the engine emission to be invisible. However, in recognition of the growing health concerns regarding ultrafine PM and especially nvPM, the CAEP/10 nvPM mass concentration certification standard was agreed at the 10th ICAO-CAEP meeting in 2016 which also required the LTO mass nvPM and number nvPM emissions to be reported. The nvPM mass concentration standard is applicable to all in-production engines with a rated thrust > 26.7 kN from 1 January 2020.

2.1.2 nvPM mass and number LTO certification standards (CAEP/11 Standards)

Using standardized data collected under the CAEP/10 measurement and computation procedures, work continued in the CAEP to develop new emission standards for nvPM. At the 11th ICAO-CAEP meeting (CAEP/11 in February 2019) new emission standards for both nvPM mass and nvPM number and the corresponding additions and amendments (Chapter 4) to Annex 16 Volume II were agreed. These standards include new regulatory limits for nvPM mass and nvPM number applying to both in-production and new engine types from 1 January 2023. These new engine emissions standards are for LTO (landing and take-off) total nvPM mass and nvPM number emissions per kiloNewton (kN) of rated thrust. As part of this agreement the nvPM mass concentration standard is now considered to preserve the

¹ ICAO Annex 16 "International standards and recommended practices, Environmental protection", Volume II "Aircraft engine emissions", 4th ed. (July, 2017)

exhaust plume invisibility and there was also agreement to end the Smoke Number Standard applicability for engines of rated thrust > 26.7 kN beginning 1 January 2023. For smaller engines the Smoke Number still applies. In addition, for the purpose of modelling, CAEP/11 agreed on requirements for the reporting of system loss correction for nvPM mass and number and their calculation method.

2.2 Local Air Quality and Health Regulations

The EU's air quality directive (2008/50/EC Directive on Ambient Air Quality and Cleaner Air for Europe) sets pollutant concentrations thresholds that shall not be exceeded in a given period of time. In case of exceedances, authorities must develop and implement air quality management plans. These plans should aim to bring concentrations of air pollutants to levels below the limit values. The PM EU standards and the World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines are summarised in the table below. These apply over differing periods of time because the observed health impacts associated with the various pollutants occur over different exposure times. The WHO guideline values are set for the protection of health and are generally stricter than the comparable politically agreed EU standards.

The ambient air quality standards for PM are expressed as PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. There are currently no ambient air quality standards for ultrafine particles (typically measured as particle number, rather than mass concentrations).

Table 1. Ambient Air Quality Standards and Guidelines for Particulate Matter

Pollutant	Averaging period	WHO recommended limit values (µg/m ³)	EU 2008/50/EC Directive limits (µg/m ³)
UFP	-	No recommendation	Not regulated
PM _{2.5}	24-hour average	25	Not regulated
	1-year average	10	20
PM ₁₀	24-hour average	50	50
	1-year average	20	40

Source: [EU Air Quality Directive \(2008/50/EC\)](#), WHO, 2006, [Air quality guidelines: Global update 2005](#).

3 Uncertainties and Knowledge Gaps in Regulations

3.1 Measurements and Current Emissions Regulations

The Standard and Recommended Practices (SARPS) for the CAEP/10 and CAEP/11 nvPM are contained in the Annex 16 Volume 2 Part III Chapter 4 to the Chicago Convention. Appendix 7 to the Annex 16 Volume II contains the details of the “Instrumentation and Measurement Techniques for Non-Volatile Particulate Matter Emissions”. The procedures described in Appendix 7 provide guidelines for the acquisition of representative turbine engine non-volatile particulate matter (nvPM) exhaust samples, and their transport to, and analysis by, the nvPM sampling and measurement system all of which are considered in WP4.

There are acknowledged uncertainties associated with the nvPM mass and number sampling and measurement compliant systems specified in the SARPs. There are also uncertainties from the fuel composition, the ambient conditions during measurement and in the measurement and system loss correction calculations. The work undertaken in WP4 of RAPTOR is focussed on the quantification of uncertainty associated with the existing CAEP nvPM standards.

3.1.1 Quantification of uncertainty associated with CAEP/10 and CAEP/11 nvPM standards

The uncertainty analysis has been empirically assessed comparing two ICAO Annex 16 Volume II compliant systems, the European Union (EUR) and Swiss nvPM reference systems, simultaneously. The nvPM and gaseous emission measurements were obtained in accordance with both the ICAO standards and SAE ARP 6320² using both the EUR and Swiss nvPM reference systems in parallel.

The experiment was undertaken on a Rich-Quench-Lean (RQL) combustor rig at Cardiff University’s Gas Turbine Research Centre (GTRC) during two distinct test periods approximately 12 months apart. To enable this analysis firstly the two ICAO Annex 16

² SAE Aerospace 2017. *ARP6320 Procedure for the Continuous Sampling and Measurement of Non-Volatile Particulate Matter Emissions from Aircraft Turbine Engines.*

Volume II compliant systems (each including mass and number counting analysers) were calibrated in parallel prior to the first test.

The main aim of the testing was to compare the two compliant systems (the EUR and the SWISS) with their usual set up shortly after calibration, and then again after the 12-month prescribed calibration period. In addition to this, variations on parts of each system such as the mass measurement systems were also investigated to determine the impact of potential changes within each system: The nvPM mass measurement systems across the two compliant systems were compared (AVL MSS Swiss vs AVL MSS EUR) and within respective systems (AVL MSS vs AVL MSS2 Swiss & AVL MSS vs. Artium LII-300 EUR).

The EUR nvPM reference system was run with additional particle sizing instrumentation (Cambustion DMS-500) and the Swiss nvPM reference system was also equipped with additional particle sizing instrumentation (TSI SMPS Model 3938). During the 2nd test campaign, there were an additional two DMS-500s and a TSI EEPS as well (4 size instruments in total).

Further tests were also made with the particle size instrument, SMPS, on the Swiss system to investigate the impact of the as follows:

- with/without a catalytic stripper (Catalytic Instruments CS08);
- with different Differential Mobility Analyzers, DMAs (long DMA Model 3081A and nano DMA Model 3085); and
- with different aerosol chargers (⁸⁵Kr Model 3077A and soft x-ray Model 3088).

The full description of the methodology and results are provided in Work Package 4: PM Measurements Deliverables Report. The full technical details of the work have been/will be presented where relevant to the technical working groups SAE E-31 and ICAO-CAEP WG3. Here we provide only a high-level summary of the findings in terms of relevance to the Regulatory Framework.

3.1.1.1 Sampling & measurement system variability

Intercomparison between the EUR and Swiss systems:

The RAPTOR measurements showed that on average the two compliant systems agreed and were well within expected uncertainty levels. It should be noted that the calibration uncertainty is minimised by performing parallel calibrations of both systems before the first test.

nvPM Mass: Mass comparisons exhibited an 11% difference in the first measurement campaign and a 3% in the second measurement campaign, these differences are on average across the concentrations tested, with the EUR system reporting lower values.

The discrepancies between the measurement systems in the first campaign significantly increased at low concentrations for both mass analysers with differences of up to 40% observed, suggesting that there may be significantly different loss of the smallest and largest particles in the two compliant systems. This larger scatter at the lower concentration range will be a factor driving the overall 11% difference observed. The larger scatter was observed towards the limit of detection (LOD) of the analysers (Mass EI < 5 mg/kgfuel, 15 µg/m³) which may likely be attributed to shedding interference linked to the line cleanliness. As these larger discrepancies occurred towards the LOD and with very low EI/concentration values they would not impact on the certification against the current CAEP/11 regulatory limits for nvPM mass and number. However, In the second campaign, more regular cleanliness checks and cyclone pot cleaning to reduce shedding were undertaken which reduced the uncertainty significantly near to the LOD (differences of less than 10% were observed in mass measurements near the LOD) and contributing to the overall much lower difference between the mass measurements of the two systems (on average only 3%).

An additional difference between the setup in the first and second campaign was the diluter boxes spill exhaust connections which were interconnected in the first but not during the second. This could be contributing to some of the 11% difference in nvPM mass observed during the first test campaign by causing different losses in splitter 1 for both systems.

Overall, it is proposed that the better agreement of mass measurements during second test campaign most likely originate from improved protocols in rig operation, sampling and cleanliness checks for the final campaign, which were adopted as an outcome of lessons learned during the initial tests which highlighted discrepancies significantly increased at low mass concentrations indicating shedding of particles from the cyclone. The largest uncertainty when comparing measurements from the compliant systems may thus be how the sampling system is run rather than the system itself.

nvPM number: nvPM EI number agreement between the EUR and SWISS reference system was within ~2% on average across the number concentrations tested during first campaign and within ~0.2% during the second. Larger discrepancies at lower sizes witnessed during the first test suggest a potential condensed metallic peak as a result of combustor damage, impacting losses and counting efficiency within the EUR and Swiss APC differently. No discrepancies were observed during the second campaign, with all nvPM number data agreeing within $\pm 5\%$ of the average across all concentrations tested.

Intra-comparison of equipment within each system:

Intra-comparisons within individual systems also highlighted good agreement between different instrument types for both mass and number. The nvPM mass measurement intra-comparison between the AVL MSS and AVLMSS2 on the Swiss system, showed generally good agreement (within 2% in the first campaign and 4% in the second). The differences between the MSS and MSS2 measurements were observed to increase at lower concentrations and, after the first campaign it was hypothesised that the unheated line connecting the MSS2 to the splitter may be the cause of this discrepancy. This was tested in the second campaign and the overall agreement between the MSS and MSS2 improved from 4% to 1% but the discrepancy at lower mass was still present.

The nvPM mass measurement intra-comparison between the AVL MSS and LII on the EUR system agreed on a 1:1 basis. However, this agreement was non-linear and this correlated with GMD and mass. The nvPM mass analysers sampling from the same sampling system, namely the AVL MSS and Artium LII on the EUR system and AVL MSS and AVL MSS2 on the Swiss system generally agreed well with each other, within ~1% for the Swiss MSS Vs MSS2

when loss correction is applied, and within ~7% for the EUR LII Vs MSS. It was found that the EUR LII displayed a non-linear behaviour specific to this analyser and thought to result from the initial blackbody calibration performed when new. An additional factor in the increased scatter seen at the lower mass concentration range (<20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) in the first campaign may also be due to the MSS resonance checks being performed on zero air in the first test and on representative exhaust in the second test. Also the increased cleanliness checks and cyclone pot cleaning were undertaken in the second campaign reducing the impacts of shedding near the LOD.

For the nvPM number intra-comparison the Swiss system comparing the standard AVL APC to the secondary AVL APC equipped with two CPCs showed that the EI number for both CPCs in the secondary APC underreport values by 11% on average. This offset could be caused by additional loss in the line required to connect the secondary APC to the system or there is the potential that the offset is impacted by potential differences in VPR losses. It was also observed that two similarly specified and calibrated CPCs from different manufacturers, if sampling behind the same VPR offer good average agreement across a range of number concentrations. However, again on closer analysis it appears this agreement may be impacted by particle size. Finally, it is noted that changes to the specified sampling system, such as adding an additional short length of unheated line, should be done in a cautionary manner and may account for the relatively large approximate 11% offset witnessed between the two AVL APCs sampling on the Swiss system.

3.1.1.2 Calibration of instruments and drift

As the second test results analysis showed even better agreement than the first, the 12-month gap between the 2 campaigns shows either that the gap did not produce any drift or that all the analysers drifted similarly.

3.1.1.3 Limit of detection and quantification

In terms of operability of the sampling system, particularly at low mass concentrations towards the LOD of the analyser, it was found that current uncertainty in reported mass could likely be improved by specifying a more rigorous cleanliness check protocol with more regular cleaning of the cyclone.

Specifically, the RAPTOR experimental campaigns highlight a number of observations and potential for improvements including the following which will be shared with the E-31 committee (see Section 4):

- Particle shedding from the 1 μ m cyclone appears to significantly impact the reported EI mass measurements at low mass concentrations <10 μ g/m³. It was observed that the prescribed scheduling of cleanliness checks is not sufficient to ensure accurate mass measurement at low mass loadings.
- It is suggested that cleanliness checks and cyclone cleaning should be performed more often, particularly when measuring nvPM mass near LOD.

It was demonstrated that nvPM mass measurement on the raw line is achievable with an average agreement within 2% when compared with the diluted nvPM mass (between 3 – 18 μ g/m³ diluted) after dilution and loss corrections. This experiment demonstrated that it is possible to take an accurate diluted nvPM mass measurement down to \sim 3 μ g/m³ when performing regular cleanliness checks, cyclone cleaning and MSS resonance checks on the correct gas source. Therefore, a diluted nvPM mass Limit Of Quantification (LOQ) of 3 μ g/m³ is suggested for a regulatory compliant sampling system. This finding will be passed on as a recommendation to SAE E-31 for discussion to application for lower thrust settings.

3.1.1.4 VPR (Volatile Particle Remover) uncertainties

Particle loss through the VPR is an area of uncertainty for nvPM number reporting. In RAPTOR WP4 the losses (dilution and particle loss) through the EUR reference systems VPR were experimentally measured using soot particles generated from the RQL combustor. Data showed that within the nominal range of 15 – 100nm, the measured VPR penetrations agreed with the reported values from the manufacturers' calibrations.

Additional experiments using silver particles to extend the calibration below 15nm down to 5 nm, showed that the fitting function was not able to model the calibration, causing differences in the Dmg (*the diameter of the theoretical engine exit plane size distribution predicted by the ARP 6481 line loss tool based on the measured nvPM number and mass and other system parameters*), ksl_num (*nvPM number system loss correction factors*) and EI_num for a given input number. These additional points were also computational expensive, taking a typical model run from sub 1 minute to 1.5 – 2.5 hours. It is a recommendation that more tests are performed to verify to VPR penetrations at small sizes.

As well as extending the size range of calibration, the measured standard deviations in the penetration values were used in the uncertainty analysis. These standard deviations were approximately a factor of 6 higher than the manufacturers errors. This did not produce any noticeable difference in the calculated EI number and EI mass. See following section for an explanation.

3.1.1.5 Uncertainties in CAEP/11 nvPM Standards

Historic data and 30 hours of combustor testing has provided input data for a 'Monte-Carlo' based appraisal tool previously developed by Dr. Paul Williams (UoM) to assess systematic or random uncertainties in CAEP/11 standards (nvPM mass and nvPM number). One of the RAPTOR objectives was to see how two regulatory compliant systems compare when measuring the same source. Data collected during the second measurement campaign have been used to calculate the loss-corrected EI mass and EI number of the Swiss and EUR systems using the ARP6481 method. The results of this analysis show that the predicted parameters of the tools (Dmg; EI mass; EI number; and the standard deviation of these) generally agree within 5%. The recorded values by both systems (nvPM and system parameters) are very similar and the sampling architecture is almost identical. This should mean that the reported values are the same, and the model confirms this. In addition, the differences in the standard deviation values are not driving major differences in the EI values. This is to be expected as the uncertainty predicted by the models combines the systematic error with the standard error (standard deviation divided by the square root of the number of data points), meaning under most conditions and reported uncertainties, the systematic error is the dominate source of uncertainty.

In the line loss model, the final uncertainty in EI is determined by the combination of the systematic errors and standard error. The standard error is the standard deviation divided by the square root of the number of data points, which for each test was 60.

3.1.2 Improvement in nvPM regulatory certainty

3.1.2.1 Impact of ambient conditions on combustor generated nvPM

Additional uncertainties in reported EI nvPM associated with ambient impacts on the combustion process have been assessed using historic data, circa 80 hours of new testing (30 hours combustor rig, 50 hours liquid diffusion burner). Results show that future correction for ambient conditions may be required (analogous to EI NO_x).

A dedicated humidity experiment was performed by adding water (as steam) to the preheated primary and secondary air, first independently and then combined. The added steam was used to replicate high relative ambient humidity levels³. Water loadings of up to 5% were investigated and for the primary air, and as the % water increased the nvPM EI mass and EI number was seen to decrease. The primary air water loading of 5% resulted in a decrease in the EI by up to around 50% for nvPM mass and 60% for number, compared to the based case (i.e. 0% water). However, the secondary air water loadings showed a converse trend and the combined effect was thus inconclusive. The experiment shows that an increase in ambient relative humidity not likely to reduce the measured values of both nvPM mass and number for the RQL technology tested. However, for other technology systems humidity may have an impact. These results will be shared with the ICAO-CAEP WG3 to aid the on-going discussion on developing a potential correction for ambient conditions.

3.1.2.2 Impact of fuel composition on combustor generated nvPM

³ Crayford, A., Bowen, P., Durand, E., Pugh, D., Sevcenco, Y. and Johnson, M. 2020. [Influence of humidity and fuel hydrogen content on ultrafine non-volatile particulate matter formation in RQL gas turbine technology.](#) Presented at: Turbomachinery Technical Conference & Exposition (TURBO EXPO 2020), London, England, 22-26 June 2020.

The impact of fuel composition on nvPM emissions was also assessed during rig tests at Cardiff University, using a range of conventional and alternative fuels. It was found that increased fuel hydrogen content correlated with reductions in nvPM emissions, in line with the literature. These results add to the body of work which will help determine the likely impact of future increases of SAF blends on nvPM emissions reductions. The results obtained during the rig tests do not contradict the fuel correction factor currently applied in the CAEP/11 nvPM standards.

A further separate test campaign on the impacts of fuel composition on particulate matter emissions was also carried out and led by ONERA in WP4. The impact of ICAO Annex 16 compliant fuel composition specifications was assessed in terms of nvPM and total-PM emissions. For this a 'bespoke' Combustion Aerosol STandard (CAST) generator designed to combust liquid fuel was used to test fuels with different composition but always within the limits of ICAO Annex 16 volume II. Two different CAST test points were selected for each fuel, the first with a higher air flow ($Q_{air} = 2.0$ L/min) and the second with a lower air flow ($Q_{air} = 1.5$ L/min).

Specifically, a reference low aromatic, low sulphur Jet-A1 fuel, with a sulphur content of 4 ppm and 16% of aromatic compounds (0.5% naphthalene) was sourced. To study the impact of sulphur, 3000 ppm of sulphur was firstly blended into the reference fuel. Secondly to isolate the impact of aromatics, a 23% aromatic (3% naphthalene) fuel was produced. Finally, both the sulphur and aromatic content of the reference fuel were raised to the maximum permissible ICAO limits to obtain a high sulphur, high aromatic JetA-1 blend with 3000 ppm of sulphur and 23% aromatic, (3% naphthalene). In this separate study, the following instruments were used to measure particle number, mass and size distribution: Laser Induced Incandescence (Artium LII-300) fully compliant with the EUR system for mass measurements; a condensation particle counter CPC similar but not fully compliant to the CPC in the EUR system (because it has a cut-off of measurement of 5 nm instead of 10 nm); and a Scanning Mobility Particle Spectrometer (SMPS) and a Differential Mobility Analyzer (DMA) to measure particle size distributions

In addition to the certification type on-line measurement techniques, different filters were collected to perform off-line analysis on oxidative potential of emissions, under WP6. The filters were collected before the sample treatment, thus corresponding to the raw emissions. Two different types of filters were used, filters in quartz and filters in PTFE with two different pore sizes. Samples were collected at 5 L/min for 10 seconds.

The findings of this fuel composition study were as follows:

- For the first CAST test point: For the high sulphur fuel, nvPM mass concentrations (51%) and particle numbers (29%) reduce with decreasing aromatic (and naphthalene) content and in terms of size, the GMD was reduced by 13%; However, for the lower sulphur fuel only a small reduction in nvPM mass and particle number (4% reduction for both) was observed. The reason behind this result is still unknown, one possible reason is the point selected was not completely stable for the fuel with lower sulphur and aromatic content, leading to biased comparison with the fuel containing higher amounts of aromatic compounds.
- For the second CAST test point: the high sulphur fuel and low sulphur fuel showed the same trend with nvPM mass and particle numbers reducing with decreasing aromatic (and naphthalene) content. The nvPM mass concentration reductions were in the order of 26% for the high sulphur fuel and 42% for the low sulphur fuel. Particle numbers reduced by 6% for the high sulphur fuel and by 33% for the low sulphur fuel. A reduction of 7% in GMD was also observed for both high and low sulphur fuels when reducing the aromatic content.
- The results obtained in the test, except for those obtained for the first set point for low sulphur containing fuel, are in good agreement with previous studies, like those performed in the frame of JETSCREEN project, and go in the same direction of the CAEP/11 fuel correction.
- Overall, both fuel composition studies undertaken in WP4 support the current hydrogen-based fuel correction used in CAEP/11.

3.1.2.3 Size dependent particle losses and loss correction

Size measurements determined that different analyser types (DMS-500, EEPS & SMPS)⁴ offered good agreement in terms of particle size and shape. In terms of uncertainty associated with size dependent PM loss through the nvPM system, it was also shown that size measurements potentially offer a more rigorous opportunity for loss correction compared to the currently suggested regulatory method, particularly in the case of small particles (i.e., measured nvPM mass near LOD) and distributions which are neither lognormal nor monomodal. It was also demonstrated that good agreement (between 10 – 30% average difference for the different size analysers) could be found between regulatory number measurements and size derived number concentrations. VPR penetration data collected on aero-engine representative soot was seen to closely match that reported on the ICAO compliant calibration certification, offering confidence that current methodologies employing a diffusion flame calibration source are robust.

3.1.3 Summary of Uncertainty with CAEP/10 and CAEP/11 Standards

- ▶ Sampling & measurement system variability: Agreement between the two compliant systems is good and certainly within expected bounds.
- ▶ Calibration drift: uncertainties from drift between calibrations were likely to be minimal unless both systems had drifted in the same direction. This can be confirmed with the use of as-found calibrations.
- ▶ Systematic or random uncertainties in CAEP/11 standards (nvPM mass and nvPM number) have been calculated. The reported random errors of the two compliant systems during the RAPTOR tests (and the VPR work and reported uncertainties) had little overall impact on the predicted EI uncertainty, as the systematic errors dominate. Understanding and verifying the systematic errors prescribed by E-31 and finding ways to reduce these will help reduce the overall uncertainty.
- ▶ In terms of operability of the sampling system, particularly at low mass concentrations towards the LOD of the analyser, it was found that current uncertainty in reported mass could likely be improved by specifying a more rigorous cleanliness check protocol with more regular cleaning of the cyclone.

⁴ Particle size distributions measurements on the EUR reference system (Cambustion DMS-500s) and Swiss reference system (TSI SMPS and EEPS)

- ▶ It was demonstrated that nvPM mass can be measured on the raw line (i.e. without dilution) with both LII and an MSS. Measuring on the raw line means there is no 10/1 dilution and therefore the nvPM mass measured is 10 times higher than the usual measurement (further from LOD).
- ▶ Ambient measurement conditions correction findings: The impact of ambient relative humidity was inconclusive in the RAPTOR experiments which were conducted with RQL technology. Competing impacts were observed in the primary and secondary zones indicating that humidity impact may be combustion technology specific. Results will be shared with the ICAO-CAEP WG3 to aid the on-going discussion on developing a potential ambient conditions correction factor for the regulatory CAEP nvPM standards.
- ▶ Fuel composition correction: Findings generally agree with the data used to develop the current CAEP/11 hydrogen-based fuel correction. No change to the current fuel correction is therefore proposed from this work.
- ▶ System losses: Using particle size measurements improves the accuracy of system losses and, if system losses were to be included in certification measurements in the future, size measurements should be used (rather than using the measured nvPM number and mass to predict a size distribution). This finding is particularly valid for engines with emission concentrations approaching the LOD of the current measurement systems.

3.2 Measurements and Future Emissions Regulations

3.2.1 Potential reduction of impact of aviation nvPM post CAEP/12 (WT4.3)

3.2.1.1 Future engine technology

The most recent technology step in NO_x reduction has been the introduction of lean-burn combustors (GE's TAPS in GenX and CFM LEAP engines). Although first entering service in late 2011 the technology remained the product of only one engine company on one large engine family until a second family was introduced in mid-2017, with combustion technology essentially by the same company. These two engine families are the only lean-burn engines in service at the time of writing. In parallel, a major reduction in NO_x emissions from an advanced, rich-burn combustor occurred with the introduction of Pratt & Whitney's TALON X

combustor in the PW1100G and PW1500G series geared turbofan (GTF) engines and the PW 800 series business jet engines. Other engine manufacturers have continued to make incremental improvements in their NO_x technology. Both Lean Burn and RQL combustors were designed to control NO_x emissions in modern combustors where temperature and pressures are increasing and both technologies have been successful in controlling thermal NO_x production. In addition, Lean Burn technology also has resulted in very low emissions of nvPM compared with most RQL combustors. Further developments in premixing technology include the Lean-burn Direct Injection (LDI) and the less mature multi-point injection technology being developed by NASA which is an evolution of the existing lean-burn concept but with increased staging flexibility. NASA research into multi-point injection technology is focused on significantly increasing the number of injectors to allow better premixing and vaporization of the fuel and air. There are, however, challenges associated with this technology and the CAEP Independent Expert Integrated Review panel (IEIR)⁵ considered that it was unlikely that the technology would be ready for entry into service in the next 15 years.

3.2.1.2 *nvPM contribution from unregulated engines*

The CAEP/10 and /11 nvPM standards apply to turbofan (TF) engines with rated thrust above 26.7kN thrust. For smaller engines these regulations do not apply.

Analysis of nvPM data for two small TF engines (measured outside of RAPTOR⁶) show that overall, the nvPM characteristics (e.g. increase of GMD with thrust, GMD as a function of nvPM number / mass ratio) are in the range of what has been found for large engines with the European and the Swiss nvPM systems. Both engines would nominally pass the CAEP/10 and CAEP/11 in-production standards (if the limit line is theoretically and linearly extended down to sub 26.7 kN). Further measurements of small engines are planned in Switzerland by

⁵ ICAO Committee on Aviation Environmental Protection Report (Doc 10126) CAEP/11 Report, Independent Expert Integrated Review

⁶ Durdina, L., Brem, B.T., Schönenberger, D., Siegerist, F., Anet, J.G., Rindlisbacher, T., 2019. Nonvolatile Particulate Matter Emissions of a Business Jet Measured at Ground Level and Estimated for Cruising Altitudes. *Environmental science & technology* 53, 12865–12872. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b02513>

ZHAW after the RAPTOR completion date to help quantify the contribution from these sources.

As part of WP5 in RAPTOR, available engine data for several unregulated engines (e.g. turboshaft, some piston data) were collated. It was found that the data are often not consistent with the EEDB structure (4 x LTO modes with specific thrusts) and this hampers the use of a consistent approach to emission calculations for an aircraft fleet mix. Data for nvPM mass and number were not available for many types, although smoke number measurements were available in some cases. A spreadsheet of collated emissions data is available on the RAPTOR website.

There are no public turboprop (TP) emission data like the ones provided for jet engines in the EEDB. In addition, the non-public Swedish Ministry of Defence (FOI) data, which form a sort of standard for TP emissions, do not contain nvPM values or smoke numbers. TPs contribute typically less than 5% to the total aircraft emissions at an airport (fuel burn, NOX), nevertheless it would be a step forward and useful to develop a public Fuel Flow/EI data set for TPs including nvPM that would serve as a common reference.

During the course of WP5, a Simple Engine emission CalculaTOR (SECTOR) was developed and made available. SECTOR is a JAVA based, OpenSource program that: applies the original (Excel spreadsheet) EEDB of ICAO and FOCA (and, if available, FOI; applies additional data from ICAO 9889 and the user; calculates LTO and APU emissions; offers different methods to estimate nvPM EI number and EI mass. SECTOR can serve as a practical emission calculation tool for the setup of airport emission inventory and dispersion studies and as a reference method.

A unique and internationally agreed labelling (engine UID, like for the EEDB) for non-regulated engines would be helpful to share and exchange engine emission data and to assign engines to specific aircraft types. The public FOCA data for piston engines contains UIDs, but it is not clear if they are preserved in future versions of the data set and if they are internationally applied as a standard. The FOI data for turboprops contain an "Engine ID" which however seems not well suited to serve as a strict UID.

3.2.2 Summary of Future Standards Work

- ▶ The review of combustion technology showed that lean burn and Advanced RQL combustors have been developed in recent times principally to reduce EI NO_x. Lean burn combustor technology also leads to very low EI nvPM mass and number. However, this technology is not available across the fleet and is potentially not technologically or economically scalable to smaller engines. Future directions in technology to reduce nvPM emissions concern the fuel mixing and injection systems (for example, multipoint lean direct injection or LDI an evolution of the existing lean-burn concept but with increased staging flexibility). However, LDI technologies are not straightforward and the ICAO-CAEP Independent Expert Review considered that it would be unlikely that the technology would be ready for entry into service in the next 15 years.
- ▶ The contribution of smaller non-regulated engine emissions to nvPM emissions would be helped by more consistent reporting and database development. Analysis of nvPM data for two small TF engines shows that overall, the nvPM characteristics are in the range of what has been found for large engines with the European and the Swiss nvPM systems. Both engines would nominally pass the CAEP/10 and CAEP/11 in-production standards (if the limit line is theoretically and linearly extended down to sub 26.7 kN).
- ▶ WP5 has produced SECTOR an OpenSource tool for calculating PM airport emission inventories.

3.3 Modelling and Health

3.3.1 Modelling of nvPM and vPM contribution from aircraft engines (WP5)

The emissions indices for nvPM mass and number from aircraft engines are becoming better characterised and therefore better quantified, particularly through the CAEP/11 certification Engine Emissions DataBank (EEDB).

However, there is no standard methodology to derive effective vPM EIs (mass and number). Research is ongoing and being discussed in CAEP to eventually provide an update to the FOA4 (First Order Approximation) method in the ICAO Doc 9889 Local Air Quality Manual (which currently uses a crude methodology).

WP5 Recommendations for Future Work

- For emission inventories, effective EIs could be estimated. However, because of the dynamic nature of vPM formation, such EIs would implicitly refer to a certain distance-range from the engine exit to certain fuel properties (sulphur and water content), and to average meteorological conditions (temperature and humidity).
- For dispersion calculations, a more elaborate solution might be required that accounts for the dynamic transformation of vPM mass and number during atmospheric transport.
- To focus future research and modelling of ambient UFP mass and number concentrations, guidance from impact research would be helpful on the relevance of volatile UFP in comparison to non-volatile UFP.

3.3.2 Toxicity of ultrafine PM (WP6)

WP6 aimed to assess the hazard of jet engine exhaust, based on available literature and newly generated experimental data. There are two deliverable reports from WP6 where the experimental details and results are presented in detail (RAPTOR D6.1 - Report assessment of exhaust hazard and RAPTOR D6.2 - Knowledge Gaps and Recommendations). The aim here is to provide a summary of the findings from these deliverables especially in the context of regulation.

Ambient PM is a complex mixture of that differs in terms of size distribution and chemical composition depending on the emission source, both anthropogenic and natural, and the ambient conditions as discussed in WP5. As noted in Section 2.2 of this report, the health impacts of ambient PM are regulated in terms of mass concentrations (generally PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀). Mass concentrations of these size categories do not represent the contribution of UFP very well (due to their small size and therefore mass). Particle number concentrations

are a much better measure for UFP contributions. The role of UFP is less well understood generally has been the focus of several research projects in the scientific community. It is well known that aircraft engines emit UFP, just like any other combustion engine, albeit that particles in aircraft engine emissions are even smaller than for example those emitted by diesel engines. The contribution of UFP from aircraft operations to the ambient concentration in and around airports could be significant. This also implies that not only workers on the platforms are exposed to UFP but also people living in the vicinity of airports.

In WP6 a literature survey was performed which was focussed on the physical-chemical composition of jet engine emissions, and on the toxicity of jet engine exhaust. The literature survey on toxicity data of jet engine emissions resulted in only four research papers, and only one study in which the assessment of physical-chemical properties is combined with the toxic properties. To supplement this lack of specific literature, relevant epidemiological studies and reviews were also included in the survey. The WP6 toxicological studies focused on particles and their effects on inflammation, cytotoxicity and genotoxicity and used mice (*in vivo*) or human bronchial or dendritic cells (*in vitro*) as experimental model. Variation in experimental set-up and the small sample of studies did not allow for the differentiation between the different types and settings of jet engines and their subsequent effect on toxicity. It was found that conventional Jet A-1 aviation fuel induced more cytotoxicity (LDH⁷ release) and oxidative stress compared to HEFA blend fuel, whilst the latter caused an increase in inflammatory mediators (cytokine release). Jet engine particles at low thrust promoted the production of systemic inflammation markers (IL-6 and IL-8⁸) compared to a high thrust setting. Jet engine particles induced similar toxic responses in *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies, when compared to urban PM or diesel exhaust particles. A more robust understanding of the specific components in the whole mixture of exhaust emissions that are responsible for the observed toxicity is needed to target the most harmful constituents. This requires studies that provide both physical-chemical and toxicological data.

In addition to the literature review, RAPTOR WP6 collected new experimental toxicity data. Oxidative potential (OP) measurements of collected PM samples (from WP4) were

⁷ LDH= lactate dehydrogenase

⁸ IL-6 -8 = Interleukin-6 (or -8)

performed to support the hazard assessment. It should be noted that there a number of practical difficulties highlighted by this work in WP6. Firstly, unlike diesel or gasoline engines, running these jet engines at a test bench at full thrust is a high fuel consumption activity that makes it costly. Toxicity testing often requires exposure durations of at least an hour. In addition, due to the substantial number of variables it becomes impractical to test the hazard in experimental animals whereas most in vitro cell based assays cannot yet be seen as a standardized test due to the lack of validation and regulatory acceptance. Another aspect that must be considered is the fact that jet engines not only emit UFP but also all kinds of gaseous components that also have intrinsic toxic properties. Hence, the hazard should be assessed by testing the entire mixtures and not only the hazard of UFP. Currently hazard testing on particles is often done by first sampling material on filters and subsequently bringing the loaded filter to the hazard assessment lab where the particles must be extracted from the filters. However, the extraction efficiency is often quite low (as it is extremely hard to get the UFP off a filter), and the procedure may create several artifacts and could change the original size distribution and chemical profile.

The WP6 analysis of OP did not reveal any clear differences in reactivity of PM samples generated by combustion of the fuel types investigated in this study. In the Electron Spin Resonance and Ascorbic Acid Depletion assays, OP levels of PM samples were generally in the same range as untreated blank filters. In the DTT assay, most PM samples showed higher OP levels when compared to untreated blank samples, but there was no clear difference between the various fuel types.

Due to the lack of toxicity data (only one in vivo study available) of jet engine particles produced under different settings (engine type; fuel and thrust) no hazard index could be constructed. The generated oxidative potential data in this project did not allow for a differentiation in toxicity based on oxidative potential. Based on the literature on physical-chemical properties using different fuels it can be concluded that the reduction of sulphur and aromatic content will result in reduced emission of PM and PM precursors. This will also result in lower toxicity assuming equal toxicity of the generated PM. In addition, high thrust will promote lower emission of total hydrocarbon and less production of inflammatory markers. However, for polyaromatic hydrocarbons such as naphthalene, emissions increased

as power increased. Obviously, to allow for a proper hazard assessment of jet engine emissions, more systematic toxicological research is needed in combination with the physical-chemical properties of the jet engine exhaust.

To estimate the health risk, both exposure information and information on the hazard of these UFP is urgently needed. WP6 of the RAPTOR project has started to compile the existing knowledge and complemented this with own measurements. Yet, this is still not enough to perform a decent hazard and subsequent risk assessment and to inform risk managers about no-regret options in relationship to normal operations at an airport. Knowing the diversity of PM emissions in relation to their toxicity and health effects is crucial to establish more specific emission standards and mitigation policies. The D6.2 deliverable report summarizes knowledge gaps and provides suggestions and research recommendations on how to close these gaps from a toxicological point of view. Although no specific regulatory findings can be concluded from WP6 due to the knowledge gaps identified, the RAPTOR WP6 outcomes can be used by funding agencies to select their topics and priorities to aid research to help guide future regulation and policy decisions.

WP6 has developed a list of gaps in the knowledge area of aircraft PM toxicology as follows:

- Physical-chemical characterisation and toxicity: There is no standard methodology to characterise the exhaust and to assess the hazard.
- Comparison: There is only one study in which the assessment of physical-chemical properties is combined with the toxic properties, which allows hazard assessment of different scenarios.
- Combination: Analysis of aviation emissions are either physical or chemical analysis. Research papers with extensive analytical data on both physical and chemical composition are scarce.
- Variation: Large variation of parameters in the different publications when comparing the different entries making the analytical data difficult to compare. Variation in parameters engine type, fuels, mode of operation, sampling methods, sampling techniques a number/type of compounds analysed.

- Emission data: Lack of numerical data as outcomes are mainly displayed graphically and even supporting information did not contain numerical data.
- Hazard data: studies on hazard assessment are scarce and with low consistency in methods and measured biomarkers.
- Information: Information on aircraft emissions remains inadequate since the inclusion of extensive physical and chemical analysis is often limited. Additionally, the knowledge about secondary transformations in aging aircraft exhaust is still in development.
- Hazard assessment: Remains a lack of data to allow for a hazard and risk assessment of exposure to jet engine particles.

WP6 Recommendations for Future Work

- **Standardization:** A standardized test method should be developed/used to assess the hazard of engine emissions of aircrafts considering both the physical-chemical characterisation and the toxicity of the exhaust simultaneously.
- **Repetition:** A systematic toxicological research in combination with the physical-chemical properties of the jet engine exhaust, is necessary to allow for a proper hazard assessment of jet engine emissions.
- **Development of concentration-response functions:** to be used in human risk assessment to include systemic effects (not just the lungs but also impacts on other organs such as the heart, brain and blood).
- **Construction of an aggregated hazard index:** to create a suitable bridge between environmental exposure and toxicity. The index would incorporate the relative contribution to health effects, prioritised based on the estimated contribution to local PM concentrations.

WP6 notes that starting point of what might be physicochemical and toxicological characterisation could be the outcomes of previous initiatives for road traffic evaluation such as SETPOINT, Engine Toxicity Network (EngToxNet) and the 3 GV-2-2016 projects (SUREAL-23, DownToTen and PEMS4NANO).

Other recommendations from WP6 include: highlighting the need for improved exposure assessment and emission inventory data as described in RAPTOR WP5 and summarised here in Section 3.3.1; and developing a centralised database where data on physical-chemical data on exposure, toxicological data of exhaust and emissions data can be accessed to allow a proper risk assessment.

4 Dissemination to the Regulatory Community

The work undertaken in RAPTOR is focussed on the quantification of uncertainty associated with the existing CAEP nvPM standards. Dissemination to the Regulatory Community is key to a successful outcome of the project.

The main regulatory groups involved in the technical work underpinning the CAEP nvPM standards (and for any future engine emission standards) are the ICAO-CAEP Working Group 3 (also the Modelling and Database Group MDG) and the SAE-E31 Committee. EASA participates in both the CAEP groups and E-31, as do several RAPTOR partners (Table 2 provides details on the RAPTOR partners involved).

Table 2: RAPTOR partners and the Regulatory Community

Regulatory Group	RAPTOR Partners	Role
ICAO-CAEP WG3	MMU, JC, CU, ZHAW, ON	European co-rapporteur Technical members: Emissions characterization and certification group
ICAO-CAEP MDG	MMU, JC, ON	Technical members: Modelling and database for greenhouse gas emissions and local air quality emissions and dispersion modelling
SAE-31	CU, UOM, ZHAW, ON	Technical members: Development of aircraft engine sampling methodology for nvPM

Figure 1 shows the structure of the CAEP and its technical working groups involved in the development of the technical work underpinning the CAEP SARPs.

Figure 1: the ICAO structure showing the technical working groups relevant to the RAPTOR project (WG3 and MDG)

Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between EASA, the SAE-31 and WG3 in developing the technical work underpinning the nvPM standards and provides details on how information is transferred between the groups.

Figure 2: EASA, ICAO-CAEP WG3 and the SAE-31

Results have been disseminated to the regulatory community during the CAEP/12 work programme (March 2019 to February 2022) and because of the pandemic, delays to the

measurement campaigns and the necessary extension to RAPTOR, the final data from RAPTOR will also be disseminated to the CAEP/13 work programme (March 2022 to February 2025) including a period after the end of the RAPTOR project. The CAEP/13 programme, due to similar global delays in experimental work, will continue to consider this topic and the work undertaken in RAPTOR will have ongoing relevance to the nvPM work in CAEP. Tables 3 and 4 provide details of the regulatory group meetings at which RAPTOR outcomes have been, or will be, disseminated.

Table 3: ICAO-CAEP/12 and /13 and Regulatory Meetings and Dissemination of RAPTOR outcomes

Group	Date	Location	Host
WG3-5	2-6 Nov 2020	Online	ICAO
MDG-5	Nov-20	Online	ICAO
MDG-6	Jan/Feb 2021	Online	ICAO
WG3-6	12-16 April 2021	Online	ICAO
MDG-7	19-23 April 2021	Online	ICAO
WG3-7	Sep-21	Online	ICAO
MDG-8	4-8 Oct 2021	Online	ICAO
CAEP/13 WG3-1	May-22	Online	ICAO
CAEP/13 MDG	May-22	Online	ICAO
CAEP/13 WG3-2	July-22	Online	ICAO

Table 4: Other dissemination of RAPTOR outcomes to regulatory groups

Group	Date	Location
AVIATOR Health Workshop	15-Sep-20	Online
SAE E31	January 11 - 15, 2021	Online
SAE E31	June 14 - 18, 2021	Online
SAE E31	Jan-22	Online
SAE E31	20-24 Jun-22	Zurich, Switzerland

5 Summary

The Regulatory Outcomes of each WP can be summarised at a high level as follows.

5.1 Measurements and Current Emissions Regulations (WP4)

- ▶ Sampling & measurement system variability: Agreement between the two compliant systems is good and certainly within expected bounds.
- ▶ Calibration drift: uncertainties from drift between calibrations were likely to be minimal unless both systems had drifted in the same direction. This can be confirmed with the use of as-found calibrations.
- ▶ Systematic or random uncertainties in CAEP/11 standards (nvPM mass and nvPM number) have been calculated. The reported random errors of the two compliant systems during the RAPTOR tests (and the VPR work and reported uncertainties) had little overall impact on the predicted EI uncertainty as the systematic errors dominate. Understanding and verifying the systematic errors prescribed by E-31 and finding ways to reduce these will help reduce the overall uncertainty.
- ▶ In terms of operability of the sampling system, particularly at low mass concentrations towards the LOD of the analyser, it was found that current uncertainty in reported mass could likely be improved by specifying a more rigorous cleanliness check protocol with more regular cleaning of the cyclone.
- ▶ It was demonstrated that nvPM mass can be measured on the raw line (i.e. without dilution) with both and LII and an MSS. Measuring on the raw line means there is no 10/1 dilution and therefore the nvPM mass measured is 10 times higher than the usual measurement (further from LOD).
- ▶ Ambient measurement conditions correction findings: The impact of ambient relative humidity was inconclusive in the RAPTOR experiments which were conducted with RQL technology. Competing impacts were observed in the primary and secondary zones indicating that humidity impact may be combustion technology specific. Results will be shared with the ICAO-CAEP WG3 to aid the on-going discussion on developing a potential ambient conditions correction factor for the regulatory CAEP nvPM standards.

- ▶ Fuel composition correction: Findings generally agree with the data used to develop the current CAEP/11 hydrogen-based fuel correction. No change to the current fuel correction is therefore proposed from this work.
- ▶ System losses: Using particle size measurements improves the accuracy of system losses and, if system losses were to be included in certification measurements in the future, size measurements should be used (rather than using a the measured nvPM number and mass to predict a size distribution). This finding is particularly valid for engines with emission concentrations approaching the LOD of the current measurement systems.

5.2 Measurements and Future Emissions Regulations (WP4 and WP5)

- ▶ The review of combustion technology showed that lean burn and Advanced RQL combustors have been developed in recent times principally to reduce EI NOx. Lean burn combustor technology also leads to very low EI nvPM mass and number. Future directions in technology to reduce nvPM emissions concern the fuel mixing and injection systems (for example, multipoint lean direct injection or LDI an evolution of the existing lean-burn concept but with increased staging flexibility). However, LDI technologies are not straightforward and the CAEP Independent Expert Review considered that unlikely that the technology would be ready for entry into service in the next 15 years.
- ▶ The contribution of smaller non-regulated engine emissions to nvPM emissions would be helped by more consistent reporting and database development. Analysis of nvPM data for two small TF engines shows that overall, the nvPM characteristics are in the range of what has been found for large engines with the European and the Swiss nvPM systems. Both engines would nominally pass the CAEP/10 and CAEP/11 in-production standards (if the limit line is theoretically and linearly extended down to sub 26.7 kN).

5.3 Summary of Modelling and Health Review (WP5 and WP6)

- ▶ For nvPM the emissions indices for mass and number from regulated aircraft engines (the dominant source of aircraft nvPM) are becoming better characterised and therefore better quantified, particularly through the CAEP/11 certification Engine Emissions DataBank (EEDB).
- ▶ For vPM emission inventories, effective EIs could be estimated but would have to account for distance from the engine and fuel properties. For dispersion calculations, a more elaborate solution might be required that accounts for the dynamic transformation of vPM mass and number during atmospheric transport.
- ▶ To focus future research and modelling of ambient UFP mass and number concentrations, guidance from impact research would be helpful on the relevance of volatile UFP in comparison to non-volatile UFP.
- ▶ Toxicity work undertaken in RAPTOR WP6 aimed to assess the hazard of jet engine exhaust, based on available literature and newly generated experimental data. The toxicity work concluded that there remains a lack of data to allow for a hazard and risk assessment of exposure to jet engine particles, making regulatory or policy recommendations premature. However, several important knowledge gaps are listed to guide future research efforts to help future policy development.
- ▶ Areas for future research in hazard assessment have been identified as follows:
 - Standardization: A standardized test method should be developed/used to assess the hazard of engine emissions of aircrafts considering both the physical-chemical characterisation and the toxicity of the exhaust simultaneously.
 - Repetition: A systematic toxicological research in combination with the physical-chemical properties of the jet engine exhaust, is necessary to allow for a proper hazard assessment of jet engine emissions.
 - Development of concentration-response functions: to be used in human risk assessment to include systemic effects.
 - Construction of an aggregated hazard index: to create a suitable bridge between environmental exposure and toxicity. The index would incorporate the relative contribution to health effects, prioritised based on the estimated contribution to local PM concentrations.

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